

Role of pH on the formation of the coordination compounds with the Schiff base derived from 3-formylsalicylic acid and 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one[†]

D. Kumar^{a*}, A. Syamal^b, Anju Gupta^a, Mukesh Rani^c and P. K. Gupta^d

^aDepartment of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra-136 119, Haryana, India

E-mail : dkumar_nitk@yahoo.com, anju.guptac@gmail.com

^bSchool of Coordination Chemistry, D Wing, Ushanagar, Bhandup, Mumbai-400 078, India

E-mail : arunsyamal@yahoo.co.in

^cBhagwan Parshuram College of Engineering, Gohana-131 301, Haryana, India

E-mail : mukeshrani@gmail.com

^dDepartment of Chemistry, Haryana College of Technology and Management, Kaithal-136 027, Haryana, India

E-mail : praveen_gemini@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The coordination compounds of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II} with the Schiff base, LH₂ (1) (derived from the condensation of 3-formylsalicylic acid and 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one) have been synthesized at different pH. At pH = 2-3, LH₂ reacts with the above metal ions and forms the monomeric coordination compounds of the types [M(LH)₂] (2) (where M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}) and [M(LH)₂(H₂O)₂] (3-6) [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}]. At pH = 7-8, the ligand reacts with the above metal ions and forms the monomeric coordination compounds of the types [ML(MeOH)] (8-10) (where M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}), [Zr(OH)₂L(MeOH)₂] (11) and [ML(MeOH)₃] (12) (M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}). However, at pH = 7-8, the ligand reacts with Cu^{II} ions and forms the dimetallic coordination compound of the type [CuL]₂ (7). At pH = 10-11, LH₂ reacts with the above metal ions and forms the dimetallic coordination compounds of the types [ML(MeOH)]₂ (13-16) [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}]. The coordination compounds have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molecular weight, spectral (IR, reflectance, ESR and NMR) studies and the magnetic susceptibility measurements. LH₂ behaves as a monobasic bidentate ON donor, a dibasic tridentate OON donor and a dibasic tetradentate OONO donor ligand in the coordination compounds formed at pH 2-3, 7-8 and 10-11 respectively. In general, the basicity and denticity of LH₂ increase with the increase in pH.

Keywords : 4-Aminoantipyrine, 3-formylsalicylic acid, Schiff base, role of pH, variable denticity, spectral studies, coordination compounds.

Introduction

The pyrazoline derivatives are known to possess anti-fungal, antimalarial, antibacterial, insecticidal, herbicidal, anticonvulsive, antihistaminic, antipyretic, antirheumatic, hypoglycemic and antiinflammatory activities¹. Among

the pyrazoline derivatives, 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one, commonly known as 4-aminoantipyrine, a biologically active molecule, is an effective defervescent². It has been used as a marker in the study of transfer and bio-transformations of drugs in the

[†]We have suggested the removal of the confusing term 'complex' from coordination chemistry (A. Syamal, *J. Chem. Educn.*, 1985, 62, 143) and IUPAC has recently accepted our suggestion and this has been followed in the present work. The term 'complex' should not be used in coordination chemistry and the terms such as 'coordination compound' for 'complex compound', 'coordination titration' for 'complexometric titration' etc. should be used. For other suggested terms see the above reference.

human body and its metabolites are reported to exhibit a positive correlation with plasma fibronectin level in monitoring patients with chronic liver illness³. The analgesic, antimicrobial and anticancer activities of the coordination compounds of 4-aminoantipyrine are well known^{1,4}. The Schiff bases derived from 4-aminoantipyrine have been used as reagents in biological, pharmacological, clinical and analytical applications⁵. Their catalytic and biological activities are enhanced by coordination compound formation with transition metal ions⁶. Keeping in view the above importance of 4-aminoantipyrine and in continuation of our work on the Schiff bases derived from 3-formylsalicylic acid and their coordination compounds⁷, it was thought worthwhile to synthesize the coordination compounds of **1** with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II} ions at different pH. Since the ligand **1** contains the acidic groups such as -OH (phenolic) and -COOH, it is predicted that the coordination behaviour of **1** would be pH dependent. The syntheses and characterization of the coordination compounds of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II} and UO₂^{II} with **1** have been re-

ported by Nag *et al.*⁸ who synthesized the coordination compounds having the formulae [Co(L)(H₂O)]₂, [Ni(L)(H₂O)]₂, [Cu(L)(H₂O)]₂, [Pd(LH)Cl] and [UO₂(L)(H₂O)]₂. In this paper, we report the coordination compounds of **1**, which have been synthesized using different reaction conditions and are remarkably different from those reported by Nag *et al.*⁸.

Results and discussion

The curdy yellow Schiff base, LH₂ (**1**) was synthesized by following the method reported by Nag *et al.*⁸. It is sparingly soluble in MeOH, EtOH, CH₂Cl₂, CHCl₃, CCl₄, DMSO and DMF and is insoluble in H₂O. Owing to the possession of the phenolic OH and carboxylic groups, it is soluble in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. At pH 2-3 in aqueous or aqueous-methanolic me-

dium, it reacts with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II} in 2 : 1 molar ratio and forms the coordination compounds of the types [M(LH)₂] (**2**) (where M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}) and [M(LH)₂(H₂O)₂] (**3-6**) [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II}, UO₂^{II}]. The formations of the coordination compounds at pH = 2-3 are represented as shown below :

At pH = 7-8, a MeOH solution of the above metal ions reacts with a MeOH solution of **1** in 1 : 1 molar ratio and forms the coordination compounds of the types [CuL]₂ (**7**), [ML(MeOH)] (**8-10**) (where M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}), [Zr(OH)₂L(MeOH)₂] (**11**) and [ML(MeOH)]₃ (**12**) (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}) and their formations are shown below :

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[2; M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}]

[3; M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}]

[4]

[5]

[6]

Coordination compounds formed at pH 2-3

[7]

[8; M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}]

[9]

[10]

[11]

[12; M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}]

Coordination compounds formed at pH 7-8

[13; M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}]

[14]

[15]

[16]

Coordination compounds formed at pH 10-11

At pH = 10-11, a MeOH solution of the appropriate metal ion reacts with a MeOH solution of **1** in 1 : 1 molar ratio in the presence of MeONa and forms the dimetallic coordination compounds of the type [ML(MeOH)₂] (13-16) [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}]. All the coordination com-

pounds are sparingly soluble in H₂O, MeOH and EtOH but are fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO. Their molar conductance values (1.7-12.8 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in DMF show that they are non-electrolytes in DMF. The molecular weight measurements in diphenyl indicate the monomeric nature of [M(LH)₂] [where M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}], [M(LH)₂(H₂O)₂] [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}] (formed at pH 2-3), [ML(MeOH)] [where M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}], [Zr(OH)₂L(MeOH)₂] and [ML(MeOH)₃] [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}] (formed at pH 7-8) and the dimeric nature of [ML(MeOH)₂] [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}] (formed at pH 10-11). The coordination compounds [M(LH)₂] (where M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}) and [CuL]₂ are stable up to 250 °C and [M(LH)₂(H₂O)₂] [where M = Mn^{II},

Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}] remain stable up to only 139 °C. The loss of the coordinated H₂O molecules occurs between 140–155 °C. The appearance of a medium intensity and broad band at 3350–3420 cm⁻¹ due to ν(O-H) stretch, a sharp shoulder at 1650–1657 cm⁻¹ due to δ(H₂O) bending and a sharp band at 830–835 cm⁻¹ due to ω(OH) rocking mode also support the presence of coordinated H₂O molecules in these coordination compounds. The coordination compounds [ML(MeOH)] (where M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}), [Zr(OH)₂L(MeOH)₂], [ML(MeOH)₃] (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}) and [ML(MeOH)₂] (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II}, UO₂^{II}) remain stable up to only 84 °C. The loss of the coordinated MeOH molecule(s) occurs between 85–115 °C.

The infrared spectra of the Schiff base (1) and its coordination compounds were recorded in KBr pellets. LH₂ exhibits intramolecular H-bonded (carboxylic and phenolic OH groups), intramolecular H-bonded (phenolic OH and azomethine groups), ν(C=O)(carboxylic), ν(C=O)(pyrazoline), ν(C=N)(azomethine) and ν(C-O)(phenolic) stretches at 2900, 2700, 1707, 1675, 1654 and 1570 cm⁻¹ respectively. The appearance of ν(C=O)(carboxylic) stretch at the same energy in the ligand and its coordination compounds formed at pH = 2–3 suggests the non-involvement of carboxylic O atom(s) in coordination. However, the coordination compounds formed at pH = 7–8 and 10–11 exhibit the ν_{as}(COO) and ν_s(COO) stretches of the carboxylate group in the ranges : 1560–1650 and 1340–1430 cm⁻¹ respectively. The energy difference (Δν = 215–235 cm⁻¹) between ν_{as}(COO) and ν_s(COO) is >210 cm⁻¹ which indicates the monodentate nature of the carboxylate moiety⁹. All the coordination compounds, except [CuL]₂, exhibit a medium intensity and broad band at ~3420 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of O-H group which may be due to coordinated MeOH/H₂O molecules or unionized COOH group. The ν(C=O)(pyrazolinone) stretch of the ligand occurring at 1675 cm⁻¹ does not undergo a considerable change in the coordination compounds [M(LH)₂] (where M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}), [M(LH)₂(H₂O)₂] (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}) formed at pH = 2–3 and [CuL]₂, [ML(MeOH)] (where M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}), [Zr(OH)₂L(MeOH)₂] and [ML(MeOH)₃] (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}) formed at pH = 7–8 sug-

gesting the non-involvement of ketonic O atom towards coordination in these coordination compounds, while it shifts to lower energy by 20–35 cm⁻¹ in the coordination compounds [ML(MeOH)]₂ [where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II}, UO₂^{II}] formed at pH = 10–11 suggesting the coordination of pyrazolinone carbonyl oxygen atom to the metal ions in these coordination compounds. The ν(C=N)(azomethine) stretch of 1 occurring at 1654 cm⁻¹ shifts to lower energy by 14–34 cm⁻¹ in the coordination compounds suggesting the participation of azomethine N atom in coordination¹⁰. The appearance of a new band due to the ν(M-N) stretch at 460–517 cm⁻¹ in these coordination compounds also supports the involvement of azomethine N atom in coordination. The ν(C-O)(phenolic) stretch of 1 occurring at 1570 cm⁻¹ shifts to higher frequency by ≤ 10 cm⁻¹ in [M(LH)₂] (where M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}), [M(LH)₂(H₂O)₂] (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}) formed at pH = 2–3 and in [ML(MeOH)] (where M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}), [Zr(OH)₂L(MeOH)₂] and [ML(MeOH)₃] (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}) formed at pH = 7–8 supports the involvement of phenolic O atom in coordination¹¹. However, the ν(C-O)(phenolic) stretch of 1 shifts to higher frequency by > 10 cm⁻¹ in [CuL]₂ formed at pH = 7–8 and [ML(MeOH)]₂ (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)₂^{II}, MoO₂^{II} and UO₂^{II}) formed at pH = 10–11 and this indicates the presence of the oxo bridge in these dimetallic coordination compounds¹². The magnitude of the shift (≤ 10 cm⁻¹) indicates a monomeric structure for the coordination compounds formed either at pH = 2–3 or 7–8, except the coordination compound [CuL]₂ and a dimeric structure for rest of the coordination compounds which exhibit a shift of the ν(C-O)(phenolic) stretch by > 10 cm⁻¹. A new non-Schiff base band due to the ν(M-O) stretch appearing in the range 508–550 cm⁻¹ in the coordination compounds also supports the involvement of phenolic and/or carboxylic O atom(s) towards coordination. The increasing order of the ν(M-N) < ν(M-O) is as expected according to the greater dipole moment change in the M-O vibration, greater electronegativity of the O atom than N atom and shorter M-O bond length than the M-N bond length¹². The absence of a band in the range 850–950 cm⁻¹ characteristic of Zr=O moiety¹³ and the presence of a broad band due to ν(Zr-OH) stretch at

$\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the present Zr^{IV} coordination compounds suggest the formulation of these coordination compounds as $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})_2]$ and $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ and not as $[\text{ZrO}(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$, $[\text{ZrOL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{MeOH})_2]$ and $[\text{ZrOL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{MeOH})]_2$ respectively. The appearance of a band in the range $1110\text{--}1125\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\delta(\text{Zr}\text{--}\text{OH})$ bending mode also supports the above formulation of these coordination compounds¹³. Syamal *et al.*¹⁴ have developed a non-aqueous titrimetric method to distinguish the compounds possessing the $[\text{ZrO}]^{2+}$ or $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$ moiety. Oxozirconium(IV) compounds react with 3 *N* HCl and as a result, the oxo group gets protonated, while the zirconium(IV) compounds containing $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$ moiety do not add up HCl at all. The coordination compounds $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})_2]$ and $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ do not react with 3 *N* HCl in MeOH and this indicates the absence of $\text{Zr}=\text{O}$ bond in these coordination compounds. The $\nu_s(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ stretch in $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{MoO}_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ occurs at 930, 940 and 922 cm^{-1} respectively. On the other hand, the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ stretch occurs at 865, 845, 853 cm^{-1} respectively in these MoO_2^{II} coordination compounds. These bands occur in the usual ranges reported for the majority of MoO_2^{II} coordination compounds¹⁵. The IR data are indicative of the presence of a *cis*- MoO_2 moiety in the present MoO_2^{II} coordination compounds, as a *trans*- MoO_2 structure is expected to show only the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ band since $\nu_s(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ stretch is IR inactive. The *cis*- MoO_2 structure forces the tetradentate ligand to coordinate in a non-planar fashion (15)¹⁶. The absence of a band at $\sim 770\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the present MoO_2^{II} coordination compounds indicates the absence of an oligomeric structure with $\cdots\text{Mo}=\text{O}\cdots\text{Mo}=\text{O}\cdots$ interaction¹⁵. The UO_2^{II} coordination compounds $[\text{UO}_2(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (6), $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})]$ (10) and $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ (16) exhibit the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ stretch at 910, 940 and 925 cm^{-1} respectively. These bands occur in the usual range observed for the majority of *trans*- UO_2 compounds¹⁷. MeOH exhibits¹⁸ the $\nu(\text{C}\text{--}\text{O})$ (alcoholic) stretch at 1034 cm^{-1} . This band shifts to a lower energy by $59\text{--}76\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the coordination compounds suggesting the presence of coordinated MeOH molecule(s)¹⁹ in $[\text{ML}(\text{MeOH})]$ [where $\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}, \text{MoO}_2^{\text{II}}$ and UO_2^{II}], $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})_2]$ and $[\text{ML}(\text{MeOH})_3]$ [where $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$] formed at $\text{pH} = 7\text{--}8$ and in $[\text{ML}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ [where $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$,

$\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2^{\text{II}}, \text{UO}_2^{\text{II}}, \text{MoO}_2^{\text{II}}$] formed at $\text{pH} = 10\text{--}11$. Thus, on the basis of the analytical data (Table 1), valence requirements and IR spectral studies, it is proposed that 1 behaves as a monobasic bidentate ON donor, a dibasic tridentate OON donor and a dibasic tetradentate OONO donor ligand in the coordination compounds formed at $\text{pH} = 2\text{--}3, 7\text{--}8$ and $10\text{--}11$ respectively.

Reflectance spectra :

The solid state reflectance spectra of the coordination compounds of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} were recorded and their band positions are listed in Table 2. The monometallic coordination compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2]$ (formed at $\text{pH} = 2\text{--}3$) exhibits a broad *d-d* band centered at 16550 cm^{-1} due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition in the square-planar geometry²⁰. The dimetallic coordination compound $[\text{CuL}]_2$ (formed at $\text{pH} = 7\text{--}8$) exhibits a broad asymmetric band at 12500 cm^{-1} due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transition²¹. The above value is much less than that observed in the majority of normal square-planar copper(II) coordination compounds and suggests the presence of a distorted square-planar structure²¹. The dimetallic coordination compound $[\text{CuL}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ (formed at $\text{pH} = 10\text{--}11$) exhibits one band at 15250 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition indicating an octahedral environment around the metal ion²⁰. No band due to Cu-Cu interaction was observed in these bimetallic coordination compounds. We have already pointed out that in the $d^9\text{--}d^9$ and $d^1\text{--}d^1$ systems such as $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{--}\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{OV}^{\text{IV}}\text{--}\text{OV}^{\text{IV}}$ and $\text{OMo}^{\text{V}}\text{--}\text{OMo}^{\text{V}}$ the electronic spectral bands can reasonably be explained in terms of the monometallic MO diagrams²². The six-coordinate high-spin Mn^{II} ion belongs to the $3d^5$ system. The Russell-Saunders term for high-spin Mn^{II} state is 6S which changes its notation to ${}^6A_{1g}$ in an octahedral environment. The coordination compounds $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{MnL}(\text{MeOH})_3]$ and $[\text{MnL}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ exhibit three absorption bands at 15830, 19350, 24550; 15200, 19000, 25200 and 16050, 20100, 25850 cm^{-1} due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry²³. The presence of three absorption bands at 8450, 17300, 19050; 8300, 16950, 19080 and 8650, 17500, 19070 cm^{-1} due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)(\nu_3)$ transitions in the coordination compounds $[\text{Co}(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{CoL}(\text{MeOH})_3]$ and $[\text{CoL}(\text{MeOH})]_2$

Table 1. Analytical, mol. wt. and other characterization data of coordination compounds^a

Sl. no.	Compd.	Mol. formula	Mol. wt. Obsd. (Calcd.)	Obsd. (Calcd.) %			
				M	C	H	N
1.	LH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	351.0 (351.0)	-	64.62 (64.96)	4.63 (4.84)	11.73 (11.97)
2.	[Cu(LH) ₂]	CuC ₃₈ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₈	757.2 (763.5)	8.17 (8.32)	59.43 (59.72)	4.34 (4.19)	11.28 (11.00)
3.	[Zn(LH) ₂]	ZnC ₃₈ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₈	782.3 (765.4)	8.40 (8.54)	59.72 (59.58)	4.03 (4.18)	10.73 (10.97)
4.	[Cd(LH) ₂]	CdC ₃₈ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₈	834.7 (812.4)	13.95 (13.84)	56.34 (56.13)	3.79 (3.94)	10.56 (10.34)
5.	[Mn(LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	MnC ₃₈ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₁₀	765.6 (790.9)	6.78 (6.95)	57.86 (57.65)	4.27 (4.55)	10.78 (10.62)
6.	[Co(LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	CoC ₃₈ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₁₀	783.2 (794.9)	7.23 (7.41)	57.11 (57.36)	4.69 (4.53)	10.26 (10.57)
7.	[Ni(LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	NiC ₃₈ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₁₀	813.6 (794.7)	7.45 (7.39)	57.62 (57.38)	4.58 (4.53)	10.34 (10.57)
8.	[Zr(OH) ₂ (LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	ZrC ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₂	853.5 (861.2)	10.88 (10.59)	52.61 (52.95)	4.22 (4.41)	9.52 (9.75)
9.	[MoO ₂ (LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	MoC ₃₈ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₁₂	874.6 (863.9)	11.38 (11.10)	52.53 (52.78)	4.37 (4.17)	9.61 (9.72)
10.	[UO ₂ (LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	UC ₃₈ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₁₂	1011.7 (1006.0)	23.85 (23.66)	45.08 (45.33)	3.35 (3.58)	8.17 (8.35)
11.	[CuL ₂]	Cu ₂ C ₃₈ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	841.2 (825.0)	15.51 (15.39)	55.48 (55.27)	3.79 (3.64)	10.37 (10.18)
12.	[ZnL(MeOH)]	ZnC ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	427.6 (446.4)	14.42 (14.65)	53.95 (53.77)	4.38 (4.26)	9.62 (9.40)
13.	[CdL(MeOH)]	CdC ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	511.4 (493.4)	22.95 (22.78)	48.41 (48.64)	3.97 (3.85)	8.33 (8.51)
14.	[MoO ₂ L(MeOH)]	MoC ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₇	523.6 (508.9)	18.63 (18.85)	47.38 (47.16)	3.58 (3.73)	8.37 (8.25)
15.	[UO ₂ L(MeOH)]	UC ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₇	671.7 (651.0)	36.63 (36.56)	36.62 (36.87)	2.88 (2.92)	6.33 (6.45)
16.	[Zr(OH) ₂ L(MeOH) ₂]	ZrC ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₈	511.3 (538.2)	16.79 (16.95)	46.97 (46.82)	4.52 (4.65)	7.95 (7.80)
17.	[MnL(MeOH) ₃]	MnC ₂₂ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₇	463.8 (499.9)	10.81 (10.99)	52.63 (52.81)	5.30 (5.40)	8.27 (8.40)
18.	[CoL(MeOH) ₃]	CoC ₂₂ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₇	537.6 (503.9)	11.72 (11.69)	52.17 (52.39)	5.63 (5.36)	8.48 (8.33)
19.	[NiL(MeOH) ₃]	NiC ₂₂ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₇	511.4 (503.7)	11.43 (11.65)	52.33 (52.41)	5.48 (5.36)	8.11 (8.34)
20.	[MnL(MeOH) ₂]	Mn ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₀	863.2 (871.9)	12.74 (12.60)	55.22 (55.05)	4.19 (4.36)	9.48 (9.63)
21.	[CoL(MeOH) ₂]	Co ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₀	893.5 (879.9)	13.52 (13.40)	54.67 (54.55)	4.11 (4.32)	9.72 (9.55)
22.	[NiL(MeOH) ₂]	Ni ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₀	862.1 (879.4)	13.18 (13.35)	54.82 (54.58)	4.47 (4.32)	9.68 (9.55)
23.	[CuL(MeOH) ₂]	Cu ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₀	853.6 (889.0)	14.06 (14.29)	53.62 (53.99)	4.39 (4.27)	9.22 (9.45)
24.	[ZnL(MeOH) ₂]	Zn ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₀	872.4 (892.8)	14.34 (14.65)	53.91 (53.77)	4.17 (4.26)	9.38 (9.41)
25.	[CdL(MeOH) ₂]	Cd ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₀	963.2 (986.8)	22.53 (22.78)	48.53 (48.64)	3.63 (3.85)	8.37 (8.51)
26.	[Zr(OH) ₂ L(MeOH) ₂]	Zr ₂ C ₄₀ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₁₀	1037.5 (1012.4)	18.33 (18.01)	47.32 (47.41)	4.33 (4.15)	8.46 (8.30)
27.	[MoO ₂ L(MeOH) ₂]	Mo ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₄	1004.6 (1017.9)	18.62 (18.85)	47.29 (47.16)	3.95 (3.73)	8.05 (8.25)
28.	[UO ₂ L(MeOH) ₂]	U ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₁₄	1343.6 (1302.0)	36.71 (36.56)	36.62 (36.87)	2.80 (2.92)	6.63 (6.45)

Abbreviation : ^aLH₂ = 1.

Table 2. Magnetic susceptibility measurements, reflectance and ESR spectral data of the compounds

Sl. no.	Compd.	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Reflectance spectra (cm ⁻¹)	ESR spectral data					
				$A_{\parallel} \times 10^{-4}$ (cm ⁻¹)	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	G	g_{av}	α^2
1.	[Cu(LH) ₂]	1.81	16550	165	2.22	2.07	3.21	2.12	0.75
2.	[Mn(LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	5.94	15830, 19350, 24550						
3.	[Co(LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	4.90	8450, 17300, 19050						
4.	[Ni(LH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	3.12	8400, 14630, 24300						
5.	[CuL ₂]	1.24	12500	95	2.28	2.08	3.57	2.15	0.62
6.	[MnL(MeOH) ₃]	5.91	15200, 19000, 25200						
7.	[CoL(MeOH) ₃]	4.72	8300, 16950, 19080						
8.	[NiL(MeOH) ₃]	2.89	8600, 13800, 24000						

Table-2 (contd.)

9.	[CuL(MeOH)] ₂	1.18	15250	89	2.24	2.07	3.50	2.13	0.55
10.	[MnL(MeOH)] ₂	4.1	16050, 20100, 25850						
11.	[CoL(MeOH)] ₂	3.0	8650, 17500, 19070						
12.	[NiL(MeOH)] ₂	2.2	8900, 15300, 24450						

respectively indicates an octahedral environment around the metal ion²⁰. The electronic spectral parameters of the octahedral Co^{II} coordination compounds were calculated by the standard method²⁴ and using the free ion B value of 971 cm⁻¹ and the values are as follows : [Co(LH)₂(H₂O)₂] : $Dq = 956$ cm⁻¹, $B' = 781$ cm⁻¹, $\beta = B'/B = 0.80$, $\beta^0 = 20\%$ and CFSE = -92 kJ mol⁻¹; [CoL(MeOH)]₃ : $Dq = 941$ cm⁻¹, $B' = 793$ cm⁻¹, $\beta = 0.82$, $\beta^0 = 18\%$ and CFSE = -90 kJ mol⁻¹; [CoL(MeOH)]₂ : $Dq = 977$ cm⁻¹, $B' = 769$ cm⁻¹, $\beta = 0.79$, $\beta^0 = 21\%$ and CFSE = -94 kJ mol⁻¹. The values of the v_3/v_1 are 2.25, 2.29 and 2.20 respectively and these values fall in the usual range (2.00–2.80) observed for the majority of octahedral Co^{II} coordination compounds²⁰. The coordination compounds [Ni(LH)₂(H₂O)₂], [NiL(MeOH)]₃ and [NiL(MeOH)]₂ exhibit three absorption bands at 8400, 14630, 24300; 8600, 13800, 24000 and 8900, 15300, 24450 cm⁻¹ respectively due to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(v_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(v_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ transitions respectively suggesting an octahedral geometry around the metal ion²⁰. The spectral parameter values of the octahedral Ni^{II} coordination compounds have been calculated by the standard method²⁴ and using the free ion B value of 1030 cm⁻¹. The electronic spectral parameter values are as follows : [Ni(LH)₂(H₂O)₂] : $Dq = 840$ cm⁻¹, $B' = 866$ cm⁻¹, $\beta = 0.84$, $\beta^0 = 16\%$ and CFSE = -121 kJ mol⁻¹; [NiL(MeOH)]₃ : $Dq = 860$ cm⁻¹, $B' = 819$ cm⁻¹, $\beta = 0.80$, $\beta^0 = 20\%$ and CFSE = -124 kJ mol⁻¹; [NiL(MeOH)]₂ : $Dq = 890$ cm⁻¹, $B' = 818$ cm⁻¹, $\beta = 0.79$, $\beta^0 = 21\%$ and CFSE = -128 kJ mol. The 10 Dq values of the Co^{II} coordination compounds are greater than those of the corresponding Ni^{II} coordination compounds : [Ni(LH)₂(H₂O)₂], 8400 cm⁻¹ < [Co(LH)₂(H₂O)₂], 9560 cm⁻¹; [NiL(MeOH)]₃, 8600 cm⁻¹ < [CoL(MeOH)]₃, 9410 cm⁻¹; [NiL(MeOH)]₂, 8900 cm⁻¹ < [CoL(MeOH)]₂, 9770 cm⁻¹. This is in line with the spectrochemical series of metal ions for a given ligand, given stoichiometry and a given stereochemistry : Ni^{II} < Co^{II} ²⁵. The β^0 values of the Ni^{II} coordination compounds are comparable to those of the corresponding Co^{II} coordination compounds :

[Ni(LH)₂(H₂O)₂], 16% ~ [Co(LH)₂(H₂O)₂], 18%; [NiL(MeOH)]₂, 21% ~ [CoL(MeOH)]₂, 21%. This is in line with the nephelauxetic metal ion series in terms of β and β^0 for a given ligand, a given stoichiometry and a given stereochemistry²⁶. The values of the v_2/v_1 are 1.74, 1.60 and 1.72 respectively and these values lie in the usual range (1.6–1.8) reported for the majority of octahedral nickel(II) coordination compounds²⁰.

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectra of the copper(II) coordination compounds in DMSO at 77 K have been recorded in X-band, using 100 kHz field modulation and the g values (Table 2) are relative to the standard marker tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) ($g = 2.0028$). The spin-Hamiltonian parameters of these coordination compounds ($S = 1/2$, $I = 3/2$) have been calculated and are summarized in Table 2. The ESR spectrum of [Cu(LH)₂] in frozen solution at 77 K shows well resolved four hyperfine lines with no super-hyperfine lines. However, the half field signal ($\Delta M_s = \pm 2$) corresponding to the Cu-Cu interaction was not observed and this rules out the presence of magnetic exchange in [Cu(LH)₂] and indicates the magnetically dilute nature of [Cu(LH)₂]. The observed order of the A and g values ($A_{\parallel} > A_{\perp}$; $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$) indicate that [Cu(LH)₂] possesses a square-planar structure and the ground state²⁷ of Cu^{II} is predominantly $d_{x^2-y^2}$ (2B_1 as the ground state). Here g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} denote the effective g -values when the externally applied DC field is parallel (B_{\parallel}) and perpendicular (B_{\perp}) to the symmetry axis of the crystalline field around the paramagnetic center respectively. The geometric parameter (G), a measure of the exchange interaction is 3.21 and this value lies within the range²⁸ 2.1–3.8, consistent with the ground state $d_{x^2-y^2}$. The value of $g_{\parallel} < 2.3$ indicates a significant covalent character in the M-L bond²⁹. The spectra of [CuL]₂ and [CuL(MeOH)]₂ in frozen solution at 77 K show seven hyperfine lines ($2nI + 1 = 2 \times 2 \times (3/2) + 1 = 7$) in parallel components due to the intramolecular exchange interaction in the dimer with no super-hyperfine lines. The spectra of

$[\text{CuL}]_2$ and $[\text{CuL}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ exhibit the half-field line at ~ 1600 gauss due to $\Delta M_s = 2$ transition and conclusively proves the presence of the magnetic exchange interaction in these coordination compounds. The A_{\parallel} values (Table 2) obtained are close to half of the values of monomer species and agree well with the values reported for a Cu^{II} dimers involved in magnetic exchange interaction^{21,30}. Similarly, the g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values obtained are also close to the values reported for other dimetallic Cu^{II} coordination compounds. The covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond is indicated by g and α^2_{Cu} values. The molecular orbital coefficient, i.e. covalency parameter α^2_{Cu} (a measure of covalency of the in-plane σ -bonding) has been calculated using the equation³¹ :

$$\alpha^2_{\text{Cu}} = -(A_{\parallel}/0.036) + (g_{\parallel} - 2.0023) + 3/7(g_{\perp} - 2.0023) + 0.04$$

A value of $\alpha^2_{\text{Cu}} = 0.5$ indicates the complete covalent bonding, while the value of $\alpha^2_{\text{Cu}} = 1.0$ suggests complete ionic bonding. The observed values ($\alpha^2_{\text{Cu}} = 0.55$ – 0.75 ; Table 2) of the present copper(II) coordination compounds are less than unity and this indicates that these coordination compounds possess significant covalent character in the M–L bonding³².

NMR spectral studies :

The NMR spectra of **1** and $[\text{Zn}(\text{LH})_2]$, $[\text{ZnL}(\text{MeOH})]$ and $[\text{ZnL}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$. The chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm downfield from TMS. The prominent resonance signals of these compounds were compared with the NMR spectrum of **1** reported by Nag *et al.*⁸. The ligand **1** exhibits a singlet at δ 17.3 ppm due to the COOH proton, a sharp singlet at 13.62 ppm due to phenolic proton, a singlet at δ 9.66 ppm due to azomethine proton, multiplets between δ 7.38–7.54 ppm due to the aromatic protons, a multiplet at δ 3.30 ppm due to N–Me protons and a multiplet at δ 2.50 ppm due to C–Me protons. The occurrence of the resonance signal at the same frequency (δ 17.3 ppm) due to the COOH proton in LH_2 and $[\text{Zn}(\text{LH})_2]$ indicates the non-involvement of the carboxylic group towards coordination. The absence of this signal in $[\text{ZnL}(\text{MeOH})]$ and $[\text{ZnL}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ indicates the deprotonation of the COOH group, followed by the involvement of its O atom in coordination. The absence of the resonance signal at δ 13.62 ppm due to the phenolic proton in all the coordination compounds formed at all pH values studied indicates the

deprotonation of the phenolic OH group followed by its involvement in coordination. The signal due to azomethine proton appears at 9.66 ppm in **1**, which appears at δ 9.86–9.90 ppm in the coordination compounds. This downfield shift is indicative of the coordination of the azomethine N atom with the metal ions³³. MeOH exhibits a sharp singlet at δ 4.84 ppm due to the alcoholic proton and a singlet at δ 3.35 ppm due to the methyl protons³⁴. The appearance of resonance signals at δ 2.81–2.85 ppm due to the alcoholic proton and at δ 3.0–3.1 ppm due to the methyl protons in $[\text{ZnL}(\text{MeOH})]$ and $[\text{ZnL}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ supports the presence of MeOH in these coordination compounds, while the absence of a signal at δ \sim 3.35 ppm due to the methyl protons in $[\text{Zn}(\text{LH})_2]$ indicates the absence of MeOH in $[\text{Zn}(\text{LH})_2]$.

Magnetic susceptibility measurement :

Magnetic susceptibilities measurements were carried out by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The magnetic susceptibilities were corrected for the diamagnetism of the metal-ligand system and temperature independent paramagnetism terms (TIP)³⁵. The room temperature magnetic moments of the coordination compounds are listed in Table 2. The Cu^{II} ion belongs to the $S = 1/2$ system and since its spin-orbit coupling constant is negative³⁶, due to the presence of orbital contribution the magnetically dilute Cu^{II} compound is expected to exhibit magnetic moments higher than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.)³⁷. Accordingly, the experimental value of the magnetic moment (1.81 B.M.) of $[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2]$ is higher than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) which is characteristic of magnetically dilute copper(II) coordination compounds that have one unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital³⁸. The magnetic moment value and the absence of the half-field line at ~ 1600 gauss in the spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{LH})_2]$ indicate the magnetically dilute nature of this coordination compound. The magnetic moments of $[\text{CuL}]_2$ and $[\text{CuL}(\text{MeOH})]_2$ are 1.24 and 1.18 B.M. respectively which are less than the expected value for one unpaired electron in each Cu^{II} ion. These lower values are indicative of the presence of anti-ferromagnetic exchange interaction between two Cu^{II} ions³⁹ connected by phenoxide bridges. The presence of the half-field line at ~ 1600 gauss in the ESR spectra of these coordination compounds proves conclusively the magnetically condensed dimeric nature of these coordination compounds⁴⁰. The magnetic

moments for $[\text{Mn}(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{MnL}(\text{MeOH})_3]$ are 5.94 and 5.91 B.M. respectively which are close to spin-only value of (5.92 B.M.), indicating that these coordination compounds are high-spin and six-coordinated³⁸. The coordination compounds $[\text{Co}(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{CoL}(\text{MeOH})_3]$ possess the magnetic moment value of 4.90 and 4.72 B.M. respectively in agreement with high-spin nature in the octahedral geometry³⁹. The coordination compounds, $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{NiL}(\text{MeOH})_3]$ have magnetic moment values of 3.12 and 2.89 B.M. respectively indicating a spin-free octahedral configuration^{38,39}. The coordination compounds, $[\text{MnL}(\text{MeOH})_2]$, $[\text{CoL}(\text{MeOH})_2]$ and $[\text{NiL}(\text{MeOH})_2]$ show reduced magnetic moment value of 4.1, 3.0 and 2.2 B.M. respectively than that of the respective spin-only value. The lower magnetic moment values are due to the presence of anti-ferromagnetic exchange interaction between the two metal ions connected by phenoxide bridges. Further, the reflectance spectral data of these coordination compounds indicate the presence of octahedral environment around metal ions. The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the coordination compounds of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Zr^{IV} , MoO_2^{II} and UO_2^{II} show that they are diamagnetic in nature as expected.

Experimental

Cadmium(II) acetate dihydrate [Ranbaxy]; zinc(II) acetate dihydrate [S.D.'s fine chemicals]; dioxouranium(VI) acetate tetrahydrate, hexadecaaquaoctahydroxotetra-zirconium(IV) chloride, cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate [BDH]; nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate [Fluka] and copper(II) acetate monohydrate [IDPL]; 4-aminoantipyrine [Central Drug House (P) Ltd.] were used as received for the syntheses. 3-Formylsalicylic acid, hexadecaaquaoctahydroxotetra-zirconium(IV) acetate and bis(acetylacetonato)-dioxomolybdenum(VI) were prepared by adopting the published procedures⁴¹.

Analyses and physical measurements :

The metal contents of the respective coordination compounds were estimated by following the reported procedures⁴². The elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents) and spectral (IR, reflectance and NMR) studies were carried out at the Sophisticated Analytical Instrumentation Centre, Punjab University, Chandigarh. ESR spectra of the copper(II) coordination compounds

were recorded at Sophisticated Analytical Instrumentation Centre, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay at room temperature and 77 K in DMSO. The magnetic susceptibility measurements of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Mn^{II} coordination compounds were carried out by Gouy's method. The molar conductances of the coordination compounds were carried out in DMF with the help of a Toshniwal conductivity bridge (CL01-02A) and a dip type cell calibrated with KCl solutions. The molecular weights of the coordination compounds were determined by the Rast method using diphenyl as the solvent⁴³. The quantitative estimation of coordinated $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MeOH}$ molecules was carried out by heating the coordination compounds in an air oven at the appropriate temperatures.

Synthesis of LH₂ :

The ligand (LH_2) was prepared by following the method reported by Nag *et al.*⁸.

General method for the syntheses of $[\text{M}(\text{LH})_2]$ [where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$, Zn^{II} , Cd^{II}], $[\text{M}(\text{LH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ [where $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2^{\text{II}}$, MoO_2^{II} and UO_2^{II}]:

LH_2 (2.10 g, 6 mmol) was dissolved in aqueous NaOH solution (0.48 g, 12 mmol, 10 mL) and a yellow coloured solution was obtained. An aqueous solution of appropriate metal acetate (30–50 mL) or a MeOH solution (30 mL) of hexadecaaquatetra-zirconium(IV) acetate/bis(acetylacetonato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) (3 mmol) was added to the above yellow coloured solution. The mixture was stirred magnetically for 10 min. Glacial acetic acid was then added drop wise to the above solution till the pH of the solution became 2–3. The resulting turbid mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h and the volume of the solution was reduced to one-fifth. The coloured solids formed on cooling were suction filtered, washed with and recrystallized from water followed by washing with ether. The compounds were dried as mentioned above. Yield = 30–35%.

General method for the syntheses of $[\text{CuL}]_2$, $[\text{ML}(\text{MeOH})]$ [where $\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} , MoO_2^{II} and UO_2^{II}], $[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2\text{L}(\text{MeOH})_2]$ and $[\text{ML}(\text{MeOH})_3]$ [where $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}]:

A MeOH solution (30 mL) of LH_2 (1.05 g, 3 mmol) was added to MeOH solution (25–35 mL) of appropriate metal acetate/hexadecaaquatetra-zirconium(IV) acetate/bis(acetylacetonato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) (3 mmol) and

the mixture was heated under reflux for 3–4 h on a water bath and then cooled to room temperature. The solid products formed were suction filtered, washed with and recrystallized from MeOH followed by washing with ether. Yield = 45–60%.

General method for the syntheses of $[ML(MeOH)]_2$ [where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)_2^{II}, MoO_2^{II}$ and UO_2^{II}]:

A MeOH solution (30 mL) of LH_2 (1.05 g, 3 mmol) was added to a MeOH solution (25–35 mL) of appropriate metal acetate/hexadecaquatetrazirconium(IV) acetate/bis(acetylacetonato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) (3 mmol) and the mixture was stirred magnetically for 10 min. A 10% MeOH solution of MeONa was then added drop wise to the above solution till the pH of the solution became 10–11. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h on a water bath and the coloured solids formed on cooling were suction filtered, washed with MeOH followed by washing with ether. The compounds were dried as mentioned above. Yield = 65–70%.

Conclusion :

The syntheses of different types of coordination compounds of the same ligand have been achieved by varying the pH and solvent during the syntheses of the coordination compounds. The basicity/denticity of the Schiff base (LH_2) derived from 3-formylsalicylic acid and 4-amino-2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (4-amino-antipyrine) varies considerably with change in the pH from 2 to 11. Both the basicity and denticity of the ligand increase with the increase in pH. In the pH range 2–3, it acts as a monobasic bidentate ON donor ligand and forms monometallic coordination compounds of the type $[M(LH)_2]$ (where $M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$ and Cd^{II}) and $[M(LH)_2(H_2O)_2]$ [where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zr(OH)_2^{II}, MoO_2^{II}$ and UO_2^{II}]. In the pH range 7–8, it acts as a dibasic tridentate OON donor ligand and forms the monometallic coordination compounds of the type $[ML(MeOH)]$ (where $M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO_2^{II}$ and UO_2^{II}), $[Zr(OH)_2L(MeOH)_2]$, $[ML(MeOH)_3]$ ($M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II}) except the dimetallic coordination compound $[(CuL)_2]$ while at pH = 10–11, it acts as a dibasic tetradentate OONO donor ligand in MeOH and forms the dimetallic coordination compounds of the type $[ML(MeOH)]_2$ [where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr(OH)_2^{II}, MoO_2^{II}$ and UO_2^{II}].

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